
Meaning of the Term

“Grace” forms one of the central aspects of Pauline theology. The Greek term *charis* meaning “favour,” “free gift” or “grace” is derived from the Greek root *char*, which refers to something that produces well-being. In classical Greek this term is used in three senses: (1) a charming quality that wins favour such as graciousness or attractiveness; (2) a quality of benevolence that gives favour to inferiors; and (3) a response of thankfulness to the favour given. The first sense reveals the aesthetic aspect of *charis* and refers either to things that bring delight or to persons who are witty, tactful, and artful. The other two senses denote the ethical meaning of the term and refer both to the generosity, kindness or favour shown to the beneficiaries by the benefactors and to the thankfulness or gratitude shown to the benefactors by the beneficiaries.

In the Old Testament, the term *charis* predominantly renders the Hebrew word *chen* that refers most often to the frequently occurring phrase “find favour in someone’s eyes” (Gen 6:8; 30:27; Num 11:11; 1 Sam 16:22; 1 Kgs 11:19; Ruth 2:13, 20). The condition for the bestowal of such a favour is that the one seeking the favour should throw oneself completely on the goodwill of the one from whom the favour is sought. In the New Testament *charis* refers to God’s spontaneous, unmerited gift in Jesus Christ to sinful human beings for their salvation. Luke uses it six times and has the sense of “favour” (Lk 1:30; 2:40) or of “thanksgiving” (Lk 6:32, 33, 34). Johannine prologue contains it four times in the sense of “grace” (Jn 1:14-17) which is brought by Jesus just as the law was brought by Moses. Acts of the Apostles uses this term both in the general OT sense of “favour” (2:47; 7:10, 46; 24:27) and in the specific Christian sense of “salvation through Jesus Christ” or the “gospel” (20:32). The Letter to the Hebrews and the Book of

Revelation uses this term theologically as a quality of God to show love, kindness and concern and his readiness to help needy humans (4:16; 10:29; 12:15; 13:9; Rev 1:4; 22:21) which reflect the overtones of the Pauline usage of *charis*.

In Paul

There are a hundred occurrences of *charis* in the Pauline epistles and is used in many senses. One could summarize the Pauline usage of the word “grace” as a free, unqualified, unconditional, gratuitous *gift* from God granted sovereign and received *through faith* in Christ which removes *sin* and provides *justification* and salvation. In fact, this is the *gospel* which comes as a *blessing* from God.

A Free, Gratuitous Gift

Paul’s understanding of “grace” flows from his experience of the risen Lord Jesus Christ who was revealed to him through the “grace” of God (Gal 1:15; 1 Tim 1:14) although he was a persecutor of the Christians (Gal 1:13-14; 1 Tim 1:13). Such an unmerited experience of the grace of God became foundational for all his theological thinking and teaching, especially on grace. So he is convinced that “grace” is given by God as a free, gratuitous gift to human beings for redemption and salvation (Rom 3:24; Eph 1:6-7); this grace is unmerited (Rom 4:4; 2 Tim 1:9) and on this rest God’s promises (Rom 4:16).

Paul speaks both of the “grace of God” which is God’s free gift (Rom 5:15) and which is actually the power of God working in human beings (1 Cor 15:10) and of the “grace of the Lord Jesus Christ” (Rom 5:15; Rom 16:20; 1 Cor 16:23; 2 Cor 13:13; Gal 6:18; Phil 4:23; 1 Thess 5:28; 2 Thess 3:18) which Paul uses as a form of greeting. There are also instances when Paul speaks of both “grace of God and the Lord Jesus Christ” (1 Cor 1:4; 2 Cor 1:2; Gal 1:3; Eph 1:2; Phil 1:2), once again as a greeting. In 2 Cor 8:9 “grace” also refers to the generous activity of Jesus who, though being rich, became poor to enrich the human beings.

Basis of Call and Mission

God chooses human beings through grace (Rom 11:5. 6) and calls them through the grace of Christ (Gal 1:6). This God-given grace is the basis of apostleship (Rom 1:5) and serves as an endowment for ministry (Rom 12:3; 15:15; 1 Cor 3:10; 15:10) not only to Paul (2:9) but also to other Christians (Rom 12:6; Phil 1:7) and is extended to more and more people (2 Cor 4:15).

Obtained through Christ

The access to this grace is obtained “through” Christ (Rom 5:2), it is given according to the measure of Christ’s gift (Eph 4:7) and the immeasurable riches of grace are shown in Jesus Christ (Eph 2:7). It is both God the Father and the Lord Jesus Christ who have given comfort and good hope through grace (2 Thess 2:16) and this grace is in Christ Jesus (2 Tim 2:1).

Dominates Sin and Leads to Justification

In a world where sin was exercising dominion resulting in death, grace of God abounded all the more (Rom 5:15, 17, 20) leading to justification and to new, eternal life through Jesus Christ (Rom 5:21; Tit 3:7). The human beings are thus saved by this grace through faith (Eph 2:5, 8). Here the grace operates independently of sin and what sin has caused, but works towards annihilating sin and its effects. It serves as God’s blessing (2 Cor 9:8) and his divine assistance and help (2 Cor 12:9) strengthening the human beings in their weakness.

Replaces the Law

The law, given to human beings as a means of salvation, turned out to be counterproductive. It rather offered an opportunity to sin (Rom 7:8, 11) and could not deal with sin. That is why, those who have already received the grace of God by expressing one’s faith in Christ Jesus, cannot fall back to the prescription of the law as a means of salvation (Gal 3:1-5). Those who still hold on to the law nullify the grace (Gal 2:21) and have fallen away from it (Gal 5:4).

A Form of Greeting

Paul also innovatively uses “grace” as a form of greeting along with “peace” the traditional Jewish word for greeting: “grace and peace” from God the Father and from Lord Jesus Christ (Rom 1:7; 1 Cor 1:3; 1 Thess 1:1; 2 Thess 1:2; Tit 1:4; Philm 3). Sometimes he also adds mercy to grace and peace (1 Tim. 1:2; 2 Tim 1:2) or on occasions he uses only “grace” as a form of greeting (Eph 6:24; Col 4:18; 1 Tim 6:21; 2 Tim 4:22; Tit 3:15). There are also moments when Paul uses this term to express gratitude to God (Rom 6:17; 2 Tim 1:3; 1 Cor 10:30; 15:57; 2 Cor 2:14; 8:16; 9:15; Col 3:16) given through Jesus Christ (Rom 7:25) or gratitude given to Jesus Christ (1 Tim 1:12).

Basis of Spiritual Gifts

The Greek word *charisma* which refers to the spiritual gift, is actually the result of *charis* indicating that the spiritual gift is the “work of grace” or a “gift in grace.” Thus, a spiritual gift is something “which is freely and graciously given”. The intimate relationship between grace and a gift is vivid in 1 Cor 1:4-5, 7 where Paul writes, “I give thanks to my God always for you because of the *grace* of God that has been given you in Christ Jesus, for in every way you have been enriched in him, in speech and knowledge of every kind ... so that you are not lacking in any *spiritual gift*”. As in the case of *charis*, *charisma* too refers to the gracious act of God (Rom 5:15-16; 6:23; 11:29). In this connection it is good to remember that Paul is using *charis* also to refer to the gifts given by human beings (1 Cor 16:3; 2 Cor 8:4, 6, 7, 19).

It is neither to be Nullified nor to be Received in Vain

While explaining to the Galatian readers that to return to the practices of the law would amount to nullifying the grace received, Paul states clearly that he would never do such a thing (Gal 2:21). By implication, he is exhorting them to continue in the received grace by not reviving the practices of the law, especially the practice of circumcision. Similarly, he issues an explicit admonition in 2 Cor 6:1 urging the readers not to accept the grace of God in vain. From the context of this verse, one can understand that Paul is earnestly commanding the Corinthian Christians not to waste the grace of reconciliation that has been given to them both as a gift as a responsibility to lead the others to God.

Thus,

For Paul, Christian faith and life is founded on the “grace” of God which God gives freely to all who believe in him through Christ Jesus. It plays the double function of annihilating the domination of sin and death and of effecting salvation and reconciliation that leads to new, eternal life. Grace of God or of Christ has replaced the law and all the spiritual gifts that the Christians receive are due to this grace. It is the same grace that provides the impetus for carrying on the mission of Jesus in the world. And this grace should neither be nullified nor received in vain. Thus, in the mind of Paul, the whole of Christian vocation, life and mission is due only to grace.

About the Author

M. Paul Raj is a catholic priest of the diocese of Sivagangai, Tamil Nadu, India. He has a doctorate in Biblical Theology from the University of Innsbruck, Austria, with specialization in the Epistles of St Paul. He is at present a member of the Scripture Department at the Faculty of Theology, JD, Pune, and resides in the Papal Seminary and helps out in the formation of the seminarians.

God's "action is more than just, in the sense that it goes beyond justice and manifests itself in grace," ... "Everything is grace. Our salvation is grace. Our holiness is grace. By giving us grace, he gives us more than we deserve."

Pope Francis